

Numerical modelling of the effect of water admixtures in a helium/air parallel plate dielectric barrier discharge

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In this study, a one dimensional plasma fluid model is developed for the investigation of a helium/air dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) under different levels of water admixtures (1.5 to 2000 ppm). The model considers 53 species and 439 reaction channels and it is verified with experimental results in order to ensure its correctness. The simulation results show that water admixtures significantly affect the composition of the different ion species in the mixture. In particular, it is observed that even at low levels of water (1.5 ppm) in the mixture, the hydrate positive ions are important, while for levels higher than 50 ppm they become dominant. On the other hand, hydrate negative ions become important only at much higher levels (> 2000 ppm) of water in the mixture.

Helium DBDs at atmospheric pressure have shown very promising results in many biomedical applications, such as wound healing, treatment of cancer cells, bacterial inactivation etc. [1]–[3]. In such discharges the presence of water impurities is unavoidable and should be taken into consideration as they affect the plasma composition and plasma dynamics [4]–[7]. Water impurities originate from humidity in the ambient air and from the plasma interaction with living tissue typically residing in moist environment. Consequently, understanding the effect of the water admixtures on helium/air discharges is a prerequisite for the utilization of these devices.

Due to the very complex chemistry behind this kind of discharges (dozens of species and hundreds to thousands of reaction channels), zero dimensional global models are mostly used for these simulations [8]–[10]. These models are computationally efficient, but have limitations, as they do not consider the spatial evolution (diffusion and convective transport) of the different species in the mixture. The simulation results of these models show that even at low levels of water admixtures in the helium plasma, the hydrated ions become dominant. Furthermore, it was observed that the electronegative character of the discharge increases as the level of water increases in the helium mixture. However, hydration changes the mass and, consequently, the transport coefficients of the ions. This affects the plasma dynamics in such a way that they can no longer be analyzed with global models.

In this study, a one dimensional plasma fluid model is used [11] to investigate the effect of water admixtures (in the range of 1.5 to 2000ppm) on the chemistry of a helium/air parallel plate DBD. The model takes into account the analytical chemistry between helium, nitrogen, oxygen and water species and it is verified with experimental results in order to ensure its validity. In the plasma chemistry, 53 species and 439 reaction channels are considered.

Fig. 1 presents the concentration of the different ions species in the mixture during breakdown, for different levels of water admixtures (1.5 to 2000 ppm) in the helium/air DBD. The air composition in this study is kept constant at 30 ppm (79% N₂ and 21% O₂). From Fig. 1 it can be observed that even at very low level of water (1.5 ppm) in the mixture, the hydrate positive ions are important. At this level of water admixtures the most important positive ions are He₂⁺, N₂⁺, O₂⁺, H₂O⁺ and H₂O₃⁺. On the other hand, for the negative charge species, electrons are the most abundant with concentration of more than two orders of magnitude higher than the second highest ion negative species. The simulation results have shown that as the level of water increases in the mixture, the hydration of ions becomes faster. In

particular, for levels of water admixtures above 50 ppm, the most abundant positive ions in the mixture are the H_2O^+ , H_9O_4^+ and $\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5^+$. However, this is not the case for the hydrate negative ions. As can be seen, the concentration of negative ions increases at a much slower rate, as the level of water increases in the mixture. Particularly, their concentration starts becoming important at levels of water above 2000 ppm. However, even at this level, electrons are the most important negative species, with concentrations of one order of magnitude higher with than the second highest negative ions (H_5O_3^-).

Fig. 1: Simulation results of charge species densities during breakdown for different levels of water admixture (1.5 to 2000 ppm) in a helium/air DBD.

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